

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

EFFECT OF ANTECEDENTS OF ELECTRONIC CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (E-CRM) ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY

Sani Abdulsalam¹, Mohammed Inuwa², & Ibrahim Aliyu³

^{1, 2, & 3}Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Science, Sa'adu Zungur University, Bauchi State, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: saniabdul@basug.edu.ng, 08037370320

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14729556>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed at examining the effect of antecedents of E-CRM on customer loyalty while the study specific objectives are: to examine the relationship between trust, privacy, quality of service and ease of use and Customer Loyalty. Four directional hypotheses and four research questions guided the conduct of the study, The target population for this study consisted of 210,000 customers of four commercial Banks that have multiple branches within Bauchi State which are Guarantee Trust Bank (GTB), United Bank for Africa (UBA), First Bank and Zenith Bank. The study used A-priori sample size for structural equation models. Both the minimum sample size necessary to detect the desired effect size and the minimum sample size required to achieve adequate statistical power were determined was 400. Therefore, 30% was added from 400 to 520 to take care of missing or incomplete questionnaire in line with recommendation by Story and Tait. Data for the study were collected through primary sources base on distribution of questionnaires to respondent A Nonprobability sampling using purposive sampling technique was applied in selecting customers. In order to achieve the validity analysis, the scales of the statistical research instrument were examined through two types of validity tests namely: content validity, and face validity. The data collected were analyzed using partial least square-structural equation model (PLS-SEM 4). The findings indicated that privacy, quality of service and trust have significant positive effect on customer loyalty, however Ease of use has no significant positive effect on the customer loyalty. The following recommendations were made based on findings of the study: In order to increase perceptions of usefulness, banks could organize motivational sessions and educate users about potential threats to the security and privacy of themselves and their transactions, and provide solutions to avoid such threats.

Keywords: Trust, Privacy, Quality of Service and Ease of Use and Customer Loyalty

INTRODUCTION

Customer loyalty is crucial for Nigerian banks to maintain a competitive edge, drive business growth, and ensure long-term sustainability, understanding the critical background of customer loyalty in Nigerian banks is essential for developing effective strategies to enhance customer retention, drive business growth, and maintain competitiveness Alrubaiee and Al-Nazer (2020).

In the increasingly competitive landscape of modern business, fostering and sustaining long-term customer loyalty has become a critical imperative for driving growth, retention, and ultimately, success has become a crucial strategy for organizations to achieve sustainable growth and success. Trust, a fundamental component of any successful relationship,

plays a vital role in shaping customer loyalty. Privacy is nowadays an important phenomenon in this growing business environment. As the increasing number of cyber-crime threats increases, customers are reluctant to do transactions online fearing that they might be a victim of cyber-crime. Privacy/security is characterized as the “degree to which the security mechanism offers protection for customer transaction” (Liu et al., 2023). Only when customers are confident that transactions are secure and confidential information will not be compromised then only, they will make electronic transactions (Ndugbu et al., 2023) The customers are loyal to their banks when they are sure that their banks will help them if so, ever any such breach or theft of information arises Alrubaiee and Al-Nazer (2020). However, transaction security/privacy is a phenomenon in which the customers are not very confident, thus requires a need to assess this impact on customers loyalty.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigerian commercial banks have introduced mobile banking app to enhance customer experience and loyalty (CBN, 2023). However, despite its user-friendly interface and convenient features, the app has seen low adoption rates among customers. Only 20% of Bank’s customers have downloaded and actively use the mobile banking app. Banks wants to increase app adoption and customer loyalty but needs to understand the factors driving technology acceptance among its Nigerian customers (CBN, 2023).

CRM applications are widely used, numerous businesses in Bauchi State encounter challenges in realizing tangible benefits from them. The failure is often attributed to a narrow focus on customer contact processes, neglecting necessary adjustments to internal structures and systems, as emphasized by Alrubaiee and Al-Nazer (2020). According to Irani and Love, the implementation of CRM in these organizations has been primarily focused on acquiring customers rather than providing enhanced value to them.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

- i. To examine relationship between trust and Customer Loyalty
- ii. To examine the relationship between privacy and Customer Loyalty
- iii. To examine the relationship between quality of service and Customer Loyalty
- iv. To examine the relationship between ease of use and Customer Loyalty

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What is the extent of relationship between trust and Customer Loyalty?
- ii. What is the level of relationship between privacy and Customer Loyalty?
- iii. How does quality of service relate with customer Loyalty?
- iv. What is the extent at which ease of use relate with customer Loyalty?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H0₁: Trust does not significantly relate with Customer Loyalty

H0₂: Relationship does not significantly exist between privacy and Customer Loyalty

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between quality of service and Customer Loyalty

H0₄: There is no significant relationship between ease of use and Customer Loyalty

LITERATURE REVIEW

Electronic Customer Relationship Management (e-CRM) is defined by Costello and Osborne (2020) as the use of information and communication technologies to expand the volume and scope of customer service. Andaleeb, (2021) argue that e-CRM is a term that encompasses methodology and software that can assist businesses in managing long-term relationships with consumers, which contains all customer information and is accessible to all areas of the organization via a mobile channel.

Customer Loyalty: Loyalty is commitment towards particular product or service, which make the person to make repeat purchase of the product / service constantly in future. However, in last few years, it has been noticed that even the usage of same brand purchase for many years, the customer may likely to switch for another product either because of influence of the situation or because of effective marketing strategy being employed by competitors (Al-Qataweh, et. al., 2023).

Ease of Use (EOU): The perceived ease of use (PEOU) construct can be explained as the ability of learning and using an easy technological system without any effort; it can be concluded that the more the technology system is simple and easy to use, the higher the acceptance rate by users (Sevim et al., 2022). In the current research, PEOU refers to employees' willingness to use technology systems in hotels or tourism businesses, as well as their perception that these systems can make their jobs easier, especially if they are simple to learn, comprehend, and use (Dahlstrom et al., 2023).

Trust: Trust is the degree to which customers confidently rely on the ability, integrity, and benevolence of other parties to fulfil their promises (Chou, et al., 2020). It has historically been measured in terms of integrity, benevolence, and ability of the service provider to deliver its promises. Integrity refers as devoid of opportunity behaviour which include communicating what the products cannot do by exaggerating the product performance and involving in other forms of cheating behaviours like hiding charges, dishonesty in communicating the quality of product delivery.

Privacy: Privacy has to do with the protection of different types of data that are gathered (without or with the user's knowledge) during user interaction with the online system, which may affect the system usage), in retaining the existing customers and acquiring potential online customers, privacy is seen as a critical factor (Park & Kim, 2023).

Service Quality: Ziethaml et al. (2022) introduced the concept of electronic service quality (e-SQ), which is defined as "the extent to which a website facilitates efficient and effective shopping, purchasing and delivery of products and services". moreover, service quality can also refer as "the difference between customer expectation for service performance before to the service encounter and their perceptions of the service offered" (Bendall-Lyon & Powers 2020).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted survey cross-sectional research design. The target population for this study consisted of 210,000 customers of four commercial Banks that have multiple branches within Bauchi State which are Guarantee Trust Bank (GTB), United Bank for Africa, First Bank and Zenith Bank. The study used A-priori sample size for structural equation models (Soper, 2020). The study used A-priori sample size for structural equation models (Soper, 2020). Both the minimum sample size necessary to detect the desired effect size and the minimum sample size required to achieve adequate statistical power were determined was 400. Therefore, 30% was added from 400 to 520 to take care of missing or incomplete questionnaire in line with recommendation by Story and Tait (2020). Data for the study were collected using five-point Likert scale questionnaires. A Nonprobability sampling using purposive sampling technique was applied in selecting customers. In order to achieve the validity analysis, the scales of the statistical research instrument were examined through

two types of validity tests namely: content validity, and face validity. To determine the internal consistency validity and reliability of all the constructs of this study, reliability analysis was executed using SPSS. Therefore, the reliability and stability of questionnaire are determined from the score of each measurement. Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient of 0.70 and above was attained. The data collected were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS v28) and partial least square-structural equation model (PLS-SEM 4). SPSS was used to analyzed demographic information and missing values as well as outliers and partial least square-structural equation model (PLS-SEM 4) was used for structural model analysis.

RESULTS

Measurement Model (outer model)

The figure 1 and table 1 below present the measurement model of the study. In the table, loadings of items of individual construct are shown including composite reliability (CR) for internal consistency and Average Variance extracted (AVE) for construct validity. In this study Smart-PLS4 software by Ringle, Wende, and Becker (2022) was used to analyze the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The software was used to estimate the measurement model and the structural model in this study.

Figure 1: Measurement Model

Table 1: Construct Reliability and Validity Analysis

Construct	Item	Loadings	CR	CA	AVE
Customer Loyalty	CL2	0.839	0.883	0.834	0.602
	CL3	0.879			
	CL4	0.829			
	CL5	0.875			
Ease of Use	EOU1	0.784	0.852	0.739	0.657
	EOU2	0.724			
	EOU3	0.788			

	EOU4	0.680			
	EOU5	0.624			
Privacy	P1	0.673	0.858	0.779	0.602
	P2	0.782			
	P3	0.672			
	P5	0.827			
Quality of Service	QS2	0.701	0.862	0.788	0.61
	QS3	0.752			
	QS4	0.792			
	QS5	0.751			
Trust	T1	0.707	0.814	0.764	0.586
	T3	0.831			
	T4	0.818			
	T5	0.766			

The first column in the table 1 represent the construct followed by the items measuring each construct, the loadings, composite reliability (CR), cronbach alpha (CA) and average variance extracted. The loadings of items measuring the constructs of the study were greater than 0.5 which is the minimum threshold recommended by Hair et al. (2013). However, items that failed this benchmark were deleted; they include, CL1, P4, QS1, QS5 and T2. Details of their loading and cross loadings are attached as appendix to this study. All the constructs in the study met the composite reliability and cronbach alpha benchmark of 0.7 and average variance extracted of .5. The lowest CR is 0.723, the lowest CA is 0.706 while the lowest AVE is 0.523.

Discriminant Validity (HTMT)

Table 2 shows that all the constructs have achieved the requirement of discriminant validity, being empirically distinct from one another.

Table 2: Discriminant Validity (HTMT) Matrix

	CL	EOU	P	QS	T
Customer Loyalty					
Ease of Use	0.698				
Privacy	0.833	0.897			
Quality of Service	0.738	0.851	0.812		
Trust	0.895	0.723	0.66	0.688	

Structural Model (Inner model)

Having established the model fit from the measurement model, the next part is the structural model or inner model. Hair et al. (2013) identified four key criteria for assessing the structural model in PLS-SEM. These include assessments of significance of the path coefficients, coefficient of determination (R^2), the effect size (f^2), and lastly (4) predictive relevance (Q^2). However, to ascertain the direct effect of Ease of Use, Privacy, Quality of Service and Trust on Customer Loyalty, it is paramount to carry out a bootstrapping analysis. Bootstrapping was done by using 5000 subsamples using 502 cases.

Coefficient of Determination Assessment (R^2)

Coefficient of determination indicates how well a data fit a statistical model. It is a statistical model that explains how much of the variability of a factor can be used or explained by its relationship with another factor. It is calculated as a value between 0 (0%) and 1(100%), the higher the value the better the fit. The statistics measures how well the estimated regression line fits the actual data. Impliedly, it tells us how much of the changes in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variable (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The result in Table 3 shows that customer loyalty (dependent variable) has an R^2 of 0.661. This simply implies that four (4) independent variables (Quality of service, Quality of service, Ease of use Privacy and Trust) had formed and explained the phenomenon of customer loyalty 66% of variance explained capacity in the model.

Table 3: Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Constructs	R^2 Value
Customer Loyalty (CL)	0.661

Source: Researcher’s Original Construction

Effect Size (F^2)

Table 4: Effect Size

Construct	R^2 included	R^2 excluded	F^2	Effect size
Customer Loyalty	0.563	0.562	0.002	Small

The result shows the level of effect size (F^2) for all the direct relationships among the constructs of the model. It shows that 0.279 Just as it was necessary to examine the effect size and predictive relevance of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variable on the direct relationship, it is also essential to assess the effect size and predictive relevance of the moderated relationship. On this note, the first interaction term (CL) has small effect size on the endogenous variable as presented on table.

Assessment of Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

The predictive relevance of the structural model is assessed using cross-validated Predictive Ability Test (CVPAT) in table below.

Table 5: Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

Endogenous Constructs	Q^2 predict	Predictive Relevance
Customer Loyalty	0.175	Yes
Perceive Usefulness	0.335	Yes

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS4 output, 2024.

Importance-Performance Map Analysis Matrix (IPMA) Assessment

Scores for importance were extracted from the total effects of the estimated relationships in the structural model. Furthermore, the performance index values computation was carried out through rescaling the latent score to range from 0 as the lowest of performance to 100 as the highest of performance. The result of the IPMA reveals performance of the construct Ease of Use (EOU)75.102, Privacy (P)74.711, Quality of Service (QS) (75.413) and Trust (T)(79.91) while the

importance results shown that EOU 0.19, Privacy (P) 0.284, Quality of Service (QS) 0.202, and Trust(T) 0.345. Table 6 shows the detailed IPMA result for all the constructs. Given the above, it is argued that investing in the E-CRM of a construct (independent variable) that has smaller importance for the target variable (dependent variable) would be illogical since it would have a minute impact on improving the Customer Loyalty construct (Hair et al., 2017).

Table 6: IPMA Results

Construct	Importance	Performance
Ease of Use	0.19	75.102
Privacy	0.284	74.711
Quality of Service	0.202	75.413
Trust	0.345	79.91

Source: Extracted from SmartPLS4 output, 2024.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 7: Path Coefficient for Direct Relationship

Hypotheses	Relationship	Beta	Stnd Error	T-value	p-value	Decision
H1	EOU -> CL	-0.048	0.107	0.45	0.652 ***	Not Supported
H2	P -> CL	0.408	0.09	4.547	0.000***	Supported
H3	QS -> CL	0.142	0.067	2.108	0.035 ***	Supported
H4	T -> CL	0.315	0.066	4.786	0.000***	Supported

***P value <0.01, **P value<0.05 *P-value<0.1

From Table 4.11, it can be seen that EOU has no significant positive effect on the customer loyalty ($\beta = -0.048$, t-value = 0.45, p-value < 0.01). This means an increase in EOU will lead to -4.8% increase in the bank customer loyalty. Thus, the first hypothesis (H1) that state that Ease of use has significant effect on customer loyalty is rejected. Privacy also has a significant positive effect on customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.408$ and t- value = 4.547, p-value < 0.01). Hence, hypothesis two (H₂), Privacy has significant effect on customer loyalty is also accepted.

Quality of service also has a positive significant effect on customer loyalty ($\beta = 0.142$ and t- value = 2.108, p-value < 0.01). Hence, hypothesis two (H₃), Quality of service has significant effect on customer loyalty is also accepted. Trust also has a significant positive effect on CL ($\beta = 0.315$ and t- value = 4.786 p-value < 0.01). Hence, hypothesis two (H₄), Trust has significant effect on CL is also accepted.

CONCLUSION

One of the most important E-CRM is ISs that enable organizations to analyze, store and collect customer data, and contact customers to provide a comprehensive view of their customers. From the findings, it is very clear that customer loyalty is influenced by trust, privacy, ease of use and quality of service in the context of electronic banking services. The study findings indicated that Trust, Privacy, EOU and quality of service have effect on customer loyalty. The study formed that Technology Acceptance moderates the relationship between component of E-CRM and customer loyalty.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on findings:

- i. Banks should organize motivational sessions and educate users about potential threats to the security and privacy of customers and their transactions.
- ii. The online banking system designer and developers should ensure that they design websites that provide users' a

secure service to perform online transactions.

- iii. In order to increase the perceived ease of use, banks should build online banking systems that are user-friendly.
- iv. The findings of this research study suggest that the developers and designers of OBIS and the banks should carefully consider the requirements and values of potential users and ensure that online banking systems effectively meet the needs of users.

REFERENCES

- Al-Qatawneh, M. S., Al-Kasasbeh, E., & Rabbai, R. A. Q. (2023). Investigating the impact of E-CRM on customer loyalty: A case of B2B (Business to Business Zain's customers) in Zain Company in Jordan. *Humanities and Social Sciences series*, 32(4), 9-40.
- Alrubaiee, L., & Al-Nazer, N., (2020). The impact of relationship marketing orientation on customer loyalty: The customer's perspective. *Int. J. Mark. Stud.*, 2(1), 155. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijms.v2n1p155>.
- Andaleeb, S. S. (2021). An experimental investigation of satisfaction and commitment in marketing channels: The role of trust and dependence. *Journal of Retailing*, 72(1), 77–93.
- Bendall-Lyon, D., & Powers, T. L. (2020). The influence of mass communication and time on satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of Service Marketing*, 17(6), 589–608.
- Chou, S.-F., Horng, J.-S., Liu, C.-H. S., & Lin, J.-Y. (2020). Identifying the critical factors of customer behavior: An integration perspective of marketing strategy and components of attitudes. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 55, 102113.
- Costello, A. B., & Osborne, J. W. (2022), "Best practices in exploratory factor analysis: four recommendations for getting the most from your analysis", *Practical Assessment Research & Evaluation*, 10(7). 1-9.
- Dahlstrom, B. B., Bilgihan, A., Ye, B. H., Buonincontri, P., & Okumus, F. (2023). The impact of services cape on hedonic value and behavioral intentions: The importance of previous experience. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 72, 10-20.
- Liu, M., Jamil, A., Ahmad, M. S., & Ramayah, T. (2023). Modeling the effectiveness of electronic customer relationship management (E-CRM) systems: Empirical evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Management and Technology*, 19, 77-100. DOI: 10.20397/2177-6652/0.v0i0.1747.
- Ndugbu, H.H., Mansi, A.L., & Hassan, H.E. (2023). The impact of the E- CRM (expected security and convenience of website design) on E- loyalty field study on commercial banks. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research (JBRMR)*, 14(1), 106-122.
- Park, J. S., & Kim, C. (2023). Service quality, trust, specific asset investment, and expertise: Direct and indirect effects in a satisfaction-loyalty framework. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 34(4), 613–627.
- Sevim, R., Date, H., Hundewale, N., & Kammani, A. (2022). Combination of TAM and TPB in Internet banking Adoption. *International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering*, 5(1) 146-150.
- Soper D., (2020). Power, precision, and sample size estimation in sport and exercise science research. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, pp. 1-3.
- Story C., & Tait, M. (2020). Power, precision, and sample size estimation in sport and exercise science research. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 1-3.